

Academic Review on the Importance of R&D for SMEs in Turkey

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Abstract

It was often held in industrialized economies that developed nations were the only ones capable of developing inventions that might lead to large economic leaps. This was due to the educated workforce, ability, and resources available in developed countries. It was said that developing nations do not need to manufacture their own technology and might opt to buy technology from other sources rather than creating their own. This contrasted with the common perception that developing countries must build their own technology. This was in stark contrast to the

conventional viewpoint, which held that less developed nations should create their own technologies. This was in sharp contrast to the conventional viewpoint, which held that it was essential for emerging nations to develop their own homegrown technology. Again, according to this school of thinking, the advancement of technology was, in essence, a commodity that could be sold to whomever was prepared to pay the price for it. This is true of every culture that has ever existed throughout history. It was able to make it happen whenever it was needed to do so. It was believed to be one of the production inputs like labor and capital, but it was believed to be fixed in the short term, and it was believed that the corporations who would buy it would be the only users of it. New evidence gleaned from recent studies proves, however, that this presumption is incorrect. On the other hand, fresh data that was accumulated from more recent investigations proves that this assumption is incorrect. It was also thought that the knowledge that the technology held was easy to understand and, as a result, that it was accessible to all and everyone without any complications. Following this line of reasoning has resulted in general acceptance of the premise that developed forms of technology, along with any other knowledge they may include, may be shared with other people. According to this point of view, developing nations have made the decision to buy technology rather than generate it, and the arguments that were presented earlier have shown their efficacy in the face of challenges that have been encountered in practice over the course of time.

Keywords: *SMEs in Turkey, R&D, Importance of R&D, R&D, R&D and SMEs in Turkey*

1. Introduction

To begin, it was decided that technology cannot be classified as a specific commodity that may be sold. This was the first step in the process. This was the first piece of evidence. During this line of inquiry, this was the very first finding that was made. The business of buying technology comes with a high sourcing cost since it can only be given under certain circumstances that are presented as a package, and these conditions and criteria need to be accepted before the purchase can take place. This is since it is the only option to get the technology and that it is required to be provided under these terms. There was a royalty fee, which might be summed up as commissions that were payable to the licensee for making use of the technology. When the underlying technology became accessible, these fees were used as a means of revenue generation. The whole price for these products amounted to a particular amount of money when everything was added together. During the period that was covered by the contract, there was

a predetermined proportion of the total revenue that needed to be paid in order to make use of the technology. The usage of technology incurred this expense, which was paid. When confronted with circumstances such as these, the business that handled developing the technical advancement paid special attention to the foundation of sales. The customer's expenses that were incurred because of the transaction have not been given the necessary attention that has been given to other aspects of the transaction. Businesses who invest in technology run the risk of placing themselves in precarious circumstances since the vendor is not concerned with the issue of what these companies will do if they run in an environment in which expenses rise more quickly than sales prices. This is particularly relevant to consider in contexts when inflation is widespread. Obtaining water via Lulp formerly needed payment of a fee; there was a cost connected to this activity. Other one-time or recurring upfront payments include the supervision of workers by the person selling the technology throughout the factory assembly stage, payments given to specialists in exchange for a variety of technical services offered, documentation costs, and knowledge.

2. Purchased Technology

Since the technology that was acquired did not have or did not let the firm selling the technology to get the components contained in the package from other sources, additional expenses were incurred as a consequence of the outright purchase. These expenditures are a direct consequence of the purchase of the technologies. It has been suggested that what must be done is to seek and create techniques that will allow the government to help enterprises in this regard when it is essential, to transfer technology at cheap cost, and to seek and find methods that will lower such direct expenses while gaining technology. That brings the total number of tasks to three. These are responsibilities that need immediate attention and completion. These direct expenses, in addition to the first sum, are raised by extra indirect costs that are a direct outcome of the conditions of the contract.

The individuals who were selling the technology needed, as a prerequisite for concluding the transaction, that the time covered by the agreement be a considerable proportion of the product's overall lifespan. They included the stipulation that any issues that existed inside the judicial system of the nation that was issuing the document had to be resolved. This was conducted as a safety measure. This condition has been included into the contract because it was considered essential. Prohibition of export or export permit to third countries on the

condition of quantity limitation, purchase of necessary machinery and equipment from the licensor or places to be determined, quality control of the produced product by the licensor, advertisement requirement, and prohibition of transfer of technology to others regarding production and marketing activities; export permit to third countries with the condition of export ban or quantity restriction; export permit to t.

When all ancillary costs, such as opportunity costs, are considered, it was discovered that the cost of purchasing technology is rather pricey. It is essential to acknowledge that the size of marketplaces in industrialized nations and developing countries are in no way comparable to one another at all. The markets of developing nations were not a good fit for large-scale technology since they were constructed with the presumption that they would receive help from economies of scale. Additionally, these markets were designed for huge markets, continuous flow, and a high degree of automation. This is since technologies intended for large-scale applications are developed with the anticipation that they would enjoy the advantages of economies of scale once they are put into use. In these nations, the local markets were relatively underdeveloped, and there was a dearth of readily available labor to run and maintain the machinery on a continual basis. In addition to this, there was a deficiency in the number of skilled personnel. A lack of people with relevant experience was another issue.

3. Especially Suitable Technologies for Manufacturing Workshop Style Products

It was essential to either acquire the required technology or alter it in some way so that it could be employed on a smaller scale. Both possibilities were ruled out. The fact that the information that was supposed to be included in the technology that was being transferred did not have the necessary level of clarity hampered the technology's ability to be transmitted without any hiccups. Another problem was that the information that ought to have been included in the technology that was delivered was muddled. For the technology to be acceptable for usage in the new environment, it was essential to make certain modifications to the technology that was migrated. It was needed to reorganize the technological infrastructure in order to accomplish this objective. As a direct consequence of this, enterprises that are active in impoverished countries have been the exclusive benefactors of technical advancements that are charged with the responsibility of distributing the governments of such countries. Such assessments, which are conducted by considering solely the neo-colonial logic and cost and dependence connections, demonstrate, as has been said before, that a loss of both foreign financial flow and

foreign technology is experienced. A highly negative perspective about the difficulties of buying tin arose as a direct consequence of the scenario, and this eventually led to the development of this attitude. Countries that are still constructing their economies are coming to the realization that the subject of how to enhance their technological skills is of growing relevance as a matter of national significance. For this reason, distributing resources to this issue in order to ensure cooperation between universities and businesses, to make some regulations by the state, and to establish similar institutions in countries with important technology producers is extremely important. This is because distributing resources to this issue will ensure that cooperation will occur. Another discovery was made as a direct consequence of the continuation and continuation of these fights for such a significant amount of time. One of the technologies that corporations in developing nations will transfer to other countries as part of their technology exports is going to be the practice of moving away from technologies that are now used everywhere in the globe.

The actions that were taken consisted of progressively coming up with new ideas and gradually making the quality of the product that was created better. The level of technical progress, the degree of efficiency, and the potential of the industrial sector competing on worldwide markets have all improved as a direct consequence of these actions. In addition, the level of technological development has increased. In addition to this, there has been a rise in the likelihood of the manufacturing sector successfully competing on foreign markets. As a direct consequence of this, there has been a rise in the overall level of technical competence across the whole of the nation. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] Because the technological advancements that will make a breakthrough in the three major countries, increase efficiency, and reduce costs do not depend on "big" or "important" inventions, as the traditional view says, to improve and develop the technology that has been transferred. This is because of the nature of the technological developments.

This is because technological breakthroughs are on the horizon, which will offer a countrywide breakthrough, boost efficiency, and drastically cut expenditures. It has become known that exceedingly small technological advances made on a commercial basis may lead to comparable results, although to a little lesser extent. [Citation needed] In other words, research and development studies conducted by businesses to understand, integrate, and develop the technology that is currently in use in connection with their activities may lead to the development of modern technologies. These studies are conducted to improve upon the

technology that is currently in use. Typically, the goal of these activities is to enhance technology that is already in use. Most of the time, the goal of these efforts is to enhance the performance of the functions of the technology that is already being used in connection with the operations of the organization. In the guise of research and development, it wasn't enough to accomplish something that had never been done before; this was essential for any beneficial outcome to be obtained. One other choice that might have been made was to bring something fresh to the table in addition to the work that had previously been completed. It's possible that this will happen. The conduct of research and development does not necessarily need to take place in enormous labs found inside enormous corporations, or in establishments or colleges that have been specially set up by the government to conduct this aim. For instance, in a small business, an individual who is interested in finding a solution to a problem that arises during quality control or maintenance, or an entrepreneur who is looking to save materials and energy while developing new products, can be effective in their business. Both types of individuals can contribute to the success of the business. It is possible to achieve this goal by upgrading either the software or the hardware that is presently being used. To conduct this aim, one possible solution involves updating either the software or the hardware that is presently being used. It is possible that coordinated technology transfer may bring exceptionally large benefits that can be exploited when it comes to the technical competence of local communities. The passage of time has resulted in the establishment of a variety of viewpoints on the topic of the importation of technology that were once prevalent in other nations. Only those neocolonial methods that needed a bigger financial commitment were altered during this time. It is conceivable to allot resources in this direction, it is possible to construct organizations that are comparable to those in the West that manage the production of technological activities, and it is possible for technological production activities on a national level to continue. These three activities are all within one's capabilities. It is possible to do all of this without dismissing the prospect of a technological exchange.

4. Small and Medium Enterprises Known as SMEs

Small and medium-sized firms, often known as SMEs and more usually abbreviated as "SMEs," are becoming more significant, particularly in emerging nations like Turkey. The fact that they favor flexible production systems that can swiftly adapt to the circumstances of the

era, their low costs and inexpensive production costs, the additional value and employment chances that they acquire with less capital usage all help to their adaptability.

Because each of these elements plays a role in their adaptation to the economic climate of the nation. Because they have these abilities, they can adjust to the political and economic environment of the nation in the most effective manner that is open to them. When it comes to small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), being engaged in technical activities is the best way to make a name for oneself in a sector that places a premium on added value. The part of technical work that is regarded to be of the utmost importance is the quantity of work that is put into research and development. As a direct consequence of this, countries are making progress toward the aim of elevating the share of their Gross National Product (GNP) that is distributed to research and development. The rate that is assigned to research and development in Turkey is 0.58%, which is much lower than the rates that are dedicated to research and development in the European Union and in many other nations (which range between 2-4%). To put it another way, the percentage of funds that are set aside for research and development in Turkey is far smaller. On the other hand, one might say the same thing about our nation, where almost all of the businesses, 99.5% of them, fall into the category of small and medium-sized organizations. It has been stated by Gokdoan (2007) that they do not devote a sufficient number of resources to Ge. This study analyzes, analyses, and offers an overview of recent advancements in research and development (R&D), not only in Turkey but also elsewhere in the world, as well as the concepts that underpin research and development (R& D). The significance of the concepts of research and development (also known as R&D) and small and medium businesses (often known as SMEs) was underlined, and the R&D aid that is available to SMEs was spoken about. Both concepts are commonly abbreviated. The process of defining something resulted in the production of a complete framework as an added by-product of the process. Changes in areas such as the number of employees, sales size, customer portfolio, and existing machinery are the primary reasons for the differences in the definitions of small and medium-sized enterprises. In addition to the fundamental functions of businesses like management, marketing, accounting, and finance, these changes are the primary reason for the distinctions between the two business sizes (SMEs). This is the primary reason numerous definitions of small and medium-sized companies (also known as SMEs) may be found in the business world today.

Encouragement Industry, which was first released in 1927, is recognized as the first study to examine small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in Turkey, both historically and now. This is because the book was the first of its kind to be published. This holds true in any of these two scenarios. This plan was also created as a part of the process that followed the Izmir Economics Congress. That process is referred to in the next sentence as "that procedure." The development of technology since the 1970s comes to mind as a crucial factor that should be taken into consideration whenever the question of whether or not small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) will survive as a result of the increasing prevalence of enterprises in the first half of the 20th century is posed. This is because the emergence of enterprises in greater numbers during the first half of the 20th century. Dincer (1995) finds the growing trend toward autonomy in both individuals and societies as well as the transition to the information society as two of the factors that contribute to the rise in importance of small and medium-sized businesses. The other factor that contributes to this rise in importance is the transition to the information society. Another aspect that contributes to the growing significance of small and medium-sized businesses is the growing significance of globalization (SMEs). The evolution into an information society is another another element that has played a part in the growth of the significance of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). Despite their low levels of productivity, small and medium-sized businesses (also known as SMEs) play a vital part in the overall structure of the economy. This is since SMEs make up the great majority of businesses operating in the manufacturing, commerce, and service sectors. This is the case although SMEs have a poor total productivity within the framework of the economy. Even while the total productivity of smaller businesses within the economy is lower, this is nonetheless the case (Ozcan, 1995; Alpugan, 1988).

They are trying to make small businesses competitive with the 18 million SMEs that are found in the EU, which accounts for 70% of our country's commerce with foreign nations. To do this, they make advantage of the synergy that is produced by blending the history of SMEs founded on the culture of Akhism, the entrepreneurial spirit and risk-taking capacity of the Turkish people, as well as the technology and creative methods of today. When one considers the economic order as well as the place that small and medium-sized businesses have in industrialized nations, it is abundantly clear that there is a direct connection between robust economic institutions and robust SMEs. When taking into consideration the present situation of SMEs in industrialized nations, this becomes abundantly clear. This connection is

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unmistakable because of the robust interplay that exists between powerful economic institutions and powerful small and medium-sized businesses.

Because of this, the connection between them is quite clear. This is due to the intimate association that exists between robust economic systems and robust small and medium-sized businesses. The following describes the motivations for this interaction: Considering this, it is very necessary to cultivate powerful small and medium-sized businesses so that economies may be constructed on firm foundations.

The capacity of small and medium-sized businesses to concurrently adjust to changing conditions in local and international marketplaces is one of their greatest strengths. In the context of this strategy, the adaptable structure of small and medium-sized businesses not only offers a substantial and essential contribution to the economy, but it also guarantees that these businesses will continue to exist and will be able to grow in strength. This is the dual advantage that the technique offers. This is since this strategy takes into consideration the fact that businesses of this kind are more likely to adapt to a variety of facets of their surrounding environment (Ihan , 2006). There is a total of 220,030 businesses that fall under the Manufacturing Industry. This figure accounts for 89.12% of the total number of businesses that fall under the Manufacturing Industry. Most of these businesses have between one and nine people working for them.

The following is a condensed version of the various contributions that small and medium-sized firms, which account for 59.83% of the overall employment level in our nation, provide to the economy: Companies of a small and medium scale are lending their support to the development of a diverse range of company kinds within the framework of the economic system. The presence of small and medium-sized businesses makes it more difficult for monopolies to come into existence. These businesses also supply a positive contribution to the expansion of regional development and offer employment possibilities. They guarantee that cash is distributed in a manner that is fair and equal across the nation. Large companies that depend on them cannot function without them since they are necessary for the delivery of input and intermediate commodities. They do this through encouraging the dissemination of technological advancements to rural regions, which in turn adds to the progression of production technology. This is one of the ways in which they contribute to production technology. They are in a hurry to invest the family's money, even though they have very little of it available, despite the fact that they have a restricted reach (KOSGEB, 2009b).

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Research and development (R&D) as well as innovation are topics that are now being addressed all over the globe. These topics are vitally essential for the economic competitiveness, profitability, and long-term sustainability of a nation. The same can be said for the nation's small and medium-sized firms, which are referred to collectively as SMEs for short. These companies, together with their more well-established rivals, are the pillars around which the economy of our country is constructed. It is becoming more difficult for little firms to prosper and develop into something more significant in a global market that is continuing to expand. To improve their capacity to compete with bigger organizations, small and medium-sized enterprises, commonly known as SMEs, need to find a means to separate themselves from larger corporations and differentiate themselves from those larger companies. In this illustration, the significance of research and development, in addition to imaginative thinking, is brought into focus, drawing attention to an essential element of the process of differentiating factors. Research and development, in addition to the work done on innovations, are significant activities that small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), which are required to participate in if they want to make the most of the resources, they have available to them, must engage in. Research and development should also be considered for outsourcing by SMEs. The obligation to concentrate on research and development in addition to innovation is not placed on the shoulders of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) that are battling a variety of challenges, the most significant of which is financial. There are several obstacles that small and medium-sized businesses must overcome, the most significant of which are financial issues.

The fields of marketing and finance, in addition to those dealing with human resources, are going to be significantly affected as a result of these developments. Now, it is essential for businesses to develop an environment that is innovatively favorable if they want to continue to be competitive. This is something that may be done on its own by combining the efforts of the administration of the state in question with those of the business community in the state in question. The following are some examples of things to do:

"Vocational training programs should be established in schools or vocational education institutions in order to meet the intermediate staff needs of the economy and to train technical staff with the equipment needed by the companies."

It is very necessary to fortify and enhance the efficiency of innovation transfer hubs. It is also vital to increase the number of innovation transfer centers. There is a need for an increase in the level of aid supplied by the private sector. It is of the utmost importance to strengthen the collaboration that exists between businesses, educational institutions, and research organizations. Simplifying the complex structures of incentive mechanisms, cutting practices that are ambiguous and contradictory, and developing special information programs for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are all things that should be done in order for these businesses to be able to benefit from government incentives and other forms of incentives. Financing hurdles, as well as difficulties in buying credit, must be avoided at all costs, and circumstances that inspire confidence must be created. [Small and medium businesses (SMEs)] should be able to receive help from government incentives and other kinds of finance, and these firms should be able to benefit from government incentives. [Small and medium enterprises (SMEs)] should be able to receive help from government incentives. ... other methods of funding, as well as the ability of these enterprises, throughout the course of time, to adjust to the many technological and economic advancements taking place all over the globe. Establishing associated institutions together with specialized units and formulating plans are both necessary steps.

The incorporation of such a plan into the workings of a firm is of the utmost significance and must not to be disregarded because of this. To create new goods, boost production speed, and meet their production goals, these companies need to reduce obstacles associated to manufacturing and increase their output. Today, businesses of all kinds, but especially small and medium-sized online businesses (also known as SMEs), are needed to improve and scale up their production processes in order to keep their position as competitive players in their sector. This is true irrespective of the size of the company. Because of this, they will be able to preserve their assets and continue expanding at the same rate. When conducting this kind of study, it is essential to take into account not only the tastes and requirements of customers, but also the state of the world in terms of the progression of technological advancement.

management of research and development (R&D) as well as management of scientific and technological procedures and processes. Nevertheless, there is a connection between the management of research and development and the leadership of a company, as well as between the management of human resources and the structure and planning of the business. To put it another way, small and medium-sized businesses (also known as SMEs) that take part in

activities that are connected to research and development need effective planning, organization, execution, monitoring, and cooperation.

5. Research and Development Management

Specifically, in the field of manufacturing, our nation has just begun to enhance its capabilities in research and development management. The present scenario surrounding this matter, as it relates to small and medium businesses (SMEs), is sadly not where it should be. This is a problem. Because of this, its use in micro, small, and medium-sized businesses have seen some degree of restriction as a consequence. Everyone who is engaged in the company can now understand, considering the results of the investigations, that this is the scenario that has the best chance of occurring. Companies with their headquarters in countries that are members of the European Union supply the idea of "research and development" a broad range of different meanings, depending on the size and nature of the company. These perspectives encompass a broad variety of subtleties and subtly different nuances. Most small and medium-sized businesses operating in this industry believe that making financial contributions to research and development is the single most significant action they can take to secure the longevity and expansion of their companies. This is clear from the many projects that have been allotted to them by the several framework programs that are run by the European Union.

have been instrumental in making advances in a variety of areas. The following are the three distinct parts that make up this investigation: The first section of this study is dedicated to the management of research and development, in addition to supplying information about research and development in and of itself.

It is impossible to conduct an inspection without first doing research and development. Research and development management includes the following activities: adapting a modern technology to the conditions of the country; developing existing technologies; and adapting new technologies to these. These activities are conducted in order to produce a new product in accordance with scientific purposes; to increase the quality or standard of the product; to apply new techniques that are both cost-reducing and standard-raising; and to develop new production technologies. At each level, there is a discussion not only of the selected studies but also of the findings of the studies that were conducted. The term "innovation" refers to creative efforts that are made on a systematic basis to expand scientific and technical knowledge and use this knowledge in new applications. The term "innovation" may also refer to the use of this

knowledge to novel approaches to completing tasks. This work is being done under the pretext of expanding one's scientific and technological understanding. To put it another way, innovation may be seen as the process of applying previously obtained scientific and technological knowledge to circumstances that have not been examined before (Cannon , 2005).

6. Ideas and Significance Behind Research and Development Transactions in the Name of Research and Development

The term "research" refers to an investigation that is conducted in an organized manner with the goals of acquiring knowledge on any topic and uncovering something that was previously unknown. The pursuit of information or knowledge about a particular topic might be seen as one definition of research. Any field of study may be considered research according to this criteria. It is possible to separate it into two distinct subfields, which are known as theoretical research and empirical research, respectively. These two subdomains are distinct from one another in several ways. According to Goker (2004), the primary aim of research is to increase one's knowledge and comprehension of the unknowable by way of a succession of scientific and technological endeavors. It has been suggested that conducting this goal requires taking part in a diverse array of activities.

The definition of "basic research" can be found in the dictionary that was put out by the Turkish Language Institution. This definition refers to any theoretical or experimental investigation that is conducted to gain new knowledge without having a definite application aim. The dictionary published by the Turkish Language Association has this meaning among its entries. The State Planning Organization defines "basic research" as "theoretical or empirical research that appears to have no particular use or value for obtaining new knowledge about the underlying principles of a phenomenon or an observable phenomenon." The term "basic research" refers to "research that appears to have no particular use or value for obtaining new knowledge about the underlying principles of a phenomenon or an observable phenomenon." Research may either be theoretical or experimental at the most fundamental level (DPT). It is a type of work that, in a broader sense, is known as the type of work that tries to analyze the significance, structure, and interconnection of things and events by adding new assumptions, ideas, information, generalizations, and patterns to the mix. In other words, it is a type of work that tries to figure out how things and events are connected to one another. referred to as "primary

research." The word "fundamental research" refers to a form of study that aims to understand the meaning, structure, and interconnections of many things and occurrences in a more general sense. The results of this kind of investigation may be broken down even further into an exceedingly varied selection of other categories (Pruett , 1985). Research may be described as any activity that is conducted with the purpose of growing scientific knowledge but does not deal with any application of the information obtained through research. This is the most fundamental version of the word "study." "to have a deeper knowledge or understanding of the object under examination than of practical value" is the purpose of fundamental research. "to have a deeper knowledge or understanding of the item under inquiry than of theoretical value" "to have a deeper knowledge or understanding of the thing being studied" than "to have a deeper knowledge or understanding of the subject studied than is necessary for practical application" various academic institutions around the world. "to have a deeper knowledge or understanding of the subject studied than is necessary for practical application" Research That Is Actually Applied The term "applied studies" refers to research projects that are designed to answer a specific, real-world question. The creation of modern technologies and goods is one example of an applied study, as is the discovery of answers to issues that are met in practice and the implementation of the results of fundamental research. Actually, academics use the phrase "business-oriented rather than technology-driven" to characterize applied research. It has been shown that the Japanese place a significant emphasis on industrial research as the primary factor in their remarkable level of technological achievement (Babacan, 1994). Some of the innovations that have appeared as a direct result of globalization include expanding the production capacities of societies, differentiating the needs and expectations of individuals and societies, the growing necessity to follow technological innovations, and the production of new products that are based on technological innovations. During this period, it has once again become crucial to preserve a competitive edge in markets that are in a country other than one's own. Because of these developments, governments have started becoming engaged in activities related to research and development, often known as R&D. This is one of the most crucial jobs when it comes to being able to innovate. As a part of the continual endeavor to enhance the quality of life in modern nations, research and development (R&D) as well as the execution of creative activities are now of utmost significance. Because research and development as well as artistic pursuits are the two most significant aspects in accomplishing this objective. The expansion of the role played by the private sector in the aforementioned areas is one of the

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economic development goals that almost every country in the world has selected as one of its top priorities. This goal was chosen as one of the world's top priorities because it has the potential to expand the role played by the private sector. The private sector is already playing a significant role in these areas, but this target aspires to increase that participation.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which have started to come to the forefront in the economy especially since the 1980s and constitute an exceptionally large part of the total enterprises in the country's economies, contributed to the increase in employment and competitiveness, as well as to the provision of justice in the economy. SMEs are an exceptionally large part of the total enterprises in the country's economies. Small and medium-sized businesses (also known as SMEs) have been at the forefront of the economy ever since the 1980s, when they first started to occupy the vanguard of the economy. It is a reality that cannot be disputed that the contribution that these businesses make to the growth of research and development activities at the macro level is of the utmost importance. This is a fact that cannot be disputed. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) account for around 99 percent of the total number of companies throughout most countries, including both developed and developing nations. Due to the scale of these businesses and the role they play in the operation of the economy, it is inconceivable that a nation could expand its research and development (R&D) operations only with the contributions of its own major corporations. It is difficult for a country to depend entirely on the contributions produced by its large corporations when both variables are taken into consideration. Small and medium firms (also known as SMEs) throughout the globe have access to a greater choice of incentive programs than their bigger counterparts have. This contrasts with huge businesses, which do not have this advantage. As a direct consequence of this, supplying support to small and medium-sized businesses (often abbreviated as SMEs) in their attempts to do research and development has become a topic of significantly increased concern in all modern nations. This is particularly the case with nations that have already achieved the highest levels of technical progress. As a result of the increasing level of competition in the European Union in recent years, there has been a tendency toward a larger emphasis on research and development (R&D). This shift came about as a direct consequence of the elevated degree of competitiveness that exists inside the European Union. This is done because to the feeling that research and development is one of the most successful techniques for preserving one's position of competitive advantage in the market (EU). The European Union's (EU) innovation programs welcome the participation of small and medium-

sized firms since the EU gives priority to these types of businesses and supplies chances for them to be actively engaged. Because Turkey is a nation that has looked to become a member of the European Union, the government of Turkey is attempting to coordinate its policies for the funding of research and development with the goals of the Union. Because Turkey is a nation that has looked to join the European Union, this effort is being undertaken because of that country's interest in doing so. 2 The following are some of the goals that are intended to be carried out by this study:

- (1) To decide the perspectives of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in research and development activities in Turkey.*
- (2) to decide at what level these SMEs benefit from both direct and indirect incentives for research and development ; and*
- (3) to evaluate these perspectives in comparison with the policies and practices followed in the EU. During the investigation, previously published material on the subject was scanned and reviewed for the first time.*

This was done to make the inquiry easier to conduct. To carry out an empirical study in Turkey, a questionnaire was then sent to locals there in order to collect their responses. In addition to the findings being provided in the order that is shown below, the study is broken up into the four main sections: At the outset, a definition of the phrases "small and medium enterprises" (SMEs) is supplied for clarity. This was done in line with the primary focus of the first section of the study, which is the conceptual and theoretical framework for research and development with small and medium-sized enterprises. This was done by the major subject of the first section of the study. This was done in line with the primary focus of the first section of the investigation that was conducted. The concept of research and development, along with the activities that are related with it, is investigated to decide how they affect economic growth and the economy as a whole. The field of economics serves as the overarching backdrop for our inquiry. After that, we will talk about activities related to research and development that are conducted by SMEs as well as government incentives for these studies. The research and development activities of small and medium-sized businesses in the European Union (EU) and an examination of government incentives for such efforts are covered in the second part of the study. To facilitate better comprehension, this aspect of the study has been split into two pieces. The difficulty that we are presently facing might be seen as serious if it is evaluated within the

framework of the process of harmonization that is taking place inside the EU. In this context, after discussing the function that SMEs play in the economy of the EU, the attention shifts to the R&D activities that are conducted by SMEs as well as the incentives that are now in place. This is done after a debate has been presented on the function that SMEs play in the economy of the EU. This occurs because of and in continuation with a debate of the significance that small and medium firms have in the economy of the EU. Following an explanation of the historical evolution of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in Turkey in the second section of the study, the third section will focus on the research and development activities of SMEs and the public in Turkey. incentives for the participation in these activities These will be explained under two main headings as direct incentives and indirect incentives as tax incentives within the framework of R&D activities and the policies that were followed. Direct incentives include things like grants and loans, while indirect incentives include things like tax credits and deductions. Direct incentives include things like grants and scholarships, while indirect incentives include things like stock options. Examples of direct incentives include the following: When we talk about direct incentives, we're referring to things like grants and scholarships. When we talk about indirect incentives, however, we're referring to things like stock options. In the scope of this section, a comparison will be made between the financial incentives offered for research and development in the European Union and Turkey. In the last part of this article, the fourth section, we look at research and development (R&D) incentives for small and medium-sized businesses, using Bursa as an example of a nation that offers programs like this. We are going to talk about research and development (R&D) projects that are being conducted by small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in the next portion of this article. We will investigate the procedures that these businesses use to get things rolling. This book will investigate the role that Bursa's economy plays in the economy of Turkey as a whole, as well as the small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) that are based in Bursa and the research and development activities that they engage in. To shed light on the rise of industry in Bursa and its contribution to the city's Gross Value Added, this study was conducted. In addition, the aim of this title is to investigate the research and development efforts of these businesses in order to throw light on their rate of expansion. This administration handles and is responsible for assisting small and medium-sized businesses in growing, and it is responsible for creating chances for such growth (Çelik and Ozan, 2006, p.191). This administration handles assisting

small and medium-sized businesses, as well as creating chances for their growth, and it fulfills that responsibility.

7. Relevant Presidency

The Presidency was founded on April 12, 1990, with the passing of Law No. 3624 in order to assist small and medium-sized businesses (also known as SMEs), who occupy a significant role in the industrial sector of our nation, in adapting to advances in technical advancement. This was done to guarantee that small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) may continue to play an essential part in the industry of our nation. Small and medium-sized firms, also known as SMEs, have a significant role in our nation's industry (Çelik and Ozan, 2006, p.191). Because of this, the relevant department was founded to provide help to SMEs (Çelik and Ozan, 2006, p.191). For KOSGEB, the "Regulation on Definition, Qualifications and Classification of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises" was reorganized, and on November 18, 2005, it was published in the Official Gazette. Following the publication of the regulation for the first time, there was an extra waiting period of six months before it went into force. This principle serves as the foundation upon which KOSGEB is constructed. Article 4 of the Regulation includes a detailed explanation of the components that make up a corporation or other kind of organization. "An enterprise" is defined as "units that belong to one or more natural or legal persons and participate in an economic activity." This definition applies to enterprises regardless of their legal structure. This is true regardless of the legal structure of the organization, whether it a corporation, partnership, or sole proprietorship. The phrase "small and medium-sized companies" (SMEs) will be used throughout the course of this discussion to refer to businesses that have fewer than 250 workers and whose annual net sales revenue or financial balance sheet does not surpass 25 million New Turkish Lira. As an added point of interest, the phrase "small and medium businesses" (SMEs) is an acronym for "small and medium enterprises and micro, small and medium firms." In addition, corporations that fall under the category of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are private businesses. These organizations are categorized as micro companies, small enterprises, or medium enterprises according to the specifications of this legislation. This classification is based on the scale of the activities that they engage in. Within the wider category of small and medium companies, the regulation sets up three subcategories that organizations might use to classify themselves (SMEs). Small businesses, also known as "micro businesses," are businesses that have fewer

than 10 employees and whose annual net sales or financial balance sheet do not exceed one million New Turkish Lira. This definition of a small business also includes businesses that are sometimes referred to as "micro businesses."

When it comes to business growth, the aim of designing strategies for small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) is to expand their client base and market share, as well as their level of productivity and total earnings. These goals are included into the expansion strategies of SMEs throughout the planning process (Anyanga and Nyamita , 2016, p.11). The concept of competitiveness is brought to the forefront of the conversation whenever the expansion plans of SMEs are reviewed in terms of their advantages, as opposed to the growth plans of other SMEs, which are analyzed in terms of the strengths and weaknesses of the businesses. When doing an analysis of small and medium-sized businesses (also known as SMEs), it is critical to consider both the companies' strong points and their problematic areas. When compared to organizations of a comparable size that are not managed in a consistent and systematic way, it is generally accepted that small and medium-sized businesses have a higher level of competitiveness and efficiency. This is true even when the company in question is compared to others of the same size. This is since SMEs have organizational structures that are not as complicated as larger companies, which provides them the freedom to make choices more quickly. This pattern may be explained, in part, by the fact that small and medium-sized businesses face less competition than their larger counterparts. When competitive conditions are considered and evaluated in terms of their vulnerabilities, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), which should not be left behind in the face of developing technology, have difficulties in maintaining their existence in the market in which they operate. This is because SMEs should not be left behind in the face of developing technology. Despite the idea that small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) should not be left behind by emerging technology, this is the case. The rationale for this is to ensure that small and medium-sized businesses (also known as SMEs) do not fall behind in the race to keep up with rapidly advancing technologies. As a result, technology, even though it plays a key role in small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), is seen as required for a firm to stay competitive in its industry (Tatl, 2017, pp. 319-320). 11 According to the findings of the relevant study, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) who are interested in expanding their organizations need to supply responses to the following questions in order to do so.

8. Conclusion

When examining the degree to which a firm competes on the international market, one might see a certain phenomenon. One can see that a significant amount of emphasis is often put on the strategic role that innovation processes play inside companies in a variety of different circumstances. If we choose any one of the many examples available, we can prove that innovation is the single most essential part that contributes to the competitive advantage enjoyed by a company (Scozzi and Garavelli , 2005, p.122). Because of the lightning-fast progression of technology and the ever-increasing influence of globalization, small and medium-sized businesses, more usually referred to as SMEs, are highly attuned to the emergence of emerging trends. Small and medium-sized company (SME) managers are put in a situation where their careers might be jeopardized by companies or industries that are negatively affected by environmental circumstances, or they could be given possibilities for career growth as a positive side effect. For this reason, it is especially important for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) to forsake the conventional methods they use when developing and putting into action their strategic plans. Because it is essential vital to break free from the constraints imposed by earlier methods, this shift is needed. Because it is so important to break away from the methods that have been used traditionally, this shift is essential. Therefore, this change is significant. The managers of smaller companies need to adopt a more formal way of planning and be better prepared for the often-changing circumstances that many of their companies meet. In addition to this, they need to make sure that their staff members are aware of the significance of formal planning. These managers need to switch to a more formal planning method since the significance of strategic planning unquestionably influences the growth and development trajectory of the company (Julius et al., 2016, p.315). 12 1.3 They concluded, based on the framework that they had constructed, that higher R&D activities were promoted by worldwide rivalry. They arrived at this understanding as a result. This accomplishment was conducted while being constrained by the boundaries that they set up. They concluded that, in addition to the many kinds of innovations that are included in goods, each technique of manufacturing adds favorably to the total productivity of enterprises. After examining the pancake, they arrived at this understanding because of their findings. In addition, it has been shown that smaller and medium-sized enterprises that have been running for a longer length of time are less productive than other organizations. This was found to be the case when researchers compared the productivity of several types of businesses

(Hall , Lotti , & Mairesse , 2008:1). Zachoriadis utilized the Schumpeterian model as the foundation for his examination into how research and development (R&D) contributes to economic growth in the industrial sector of the United States. The study was undertaken to investigate how R&D contributes to economic growth. During his research, he investigated the connections between the volume of research and development conducted and the total number of patents awarded, as well as the connections between the rate of technological advancement and the total number of patents awarded, as well as the level of technological impact. The rate of economic growth is a critical factor in deciding the pace of progress. He concluded that there was a connection between all three of these different kinds of partnerships. It was proved that there is a favorable link between these attributes, as was showed in the ruling, and it was shown that this association exists (Zachoriadis , 2003: 566). Coe, Helpman, and Hoffmaister (1995) conducted a study in which they tried to establish the degree to which 77 developing nations in the south profited from the spillover impact of research and development efforts carried out in industrialized countries. Research that was conducted firsthand led to the discovery of this finding (Alti and Kaya, 2009: 252-259). Despite this, they said that spending money in research and development did not provide significant return, particularly in the near term.

9. References

- Akgemici , T. , Basic Problems of SMEs and Supports Provided, 2001.
- Alpugan , O. , Small Business Concept Establishment and Management, Karadeniz Technical University, Trabzon, 1988.
- Ankara University (2010), Kigaum.Ankara.Edu.Tr /Ozelarge.Doc
- Burpitt , W. , J., Rondinelli , D., “Small Firms ' Motivations for Export : To Earn And Learn ?”, Journal Of Small Business Management Mcoctober , 2000.
- Cabral , JEO ., Traill , WB, “ Determinants Of A Firm's likelihood to Innovate And Intensity Of Innovation In The Brazilian food Industry ”, Chain And Network Science , 1(1), 2001.
- Çalıpnar , H. , Baç, U., “ Factors Affecting Innovation in SMEs and A Field Study” Ege Academic View, 7(2), 2007.
- Çelikkaya, S. , “ A Research on R& D and Export Support in SMEs , Gebze Organized Industrial Zone”, Unpublished Master Thesis,

- Süleyman Demirel University,
Institute of Social Sciences, 2010.
- Çivi, E. , “SMEs in the New Economic Order”, I. Central Anatolia Congress Financing and Marketing Problems of SMEs , Nevşehir, October 2000.
- Çolakoğlu, M. , H., SME Directory 2002, Tobb , Kosgeb Publishing, Istanbul, 2002.
- Dinçer, Ö ., Strategic Management and Business Policy, Beta Publishing, Istanbul, 2004.
- Born; Ö.İ. , “The Effect of Quality Practices on Competitiveness of Businesses”, Published Doctoral Thesis, Dokuz Eylül University, Institute of Social Sciences, İzmir, 2000.
- Dunning , John H, “ The Globalization Of Business”, Publisher: Routledge , 1992.
- Dunning , John H, “ Towards A Taxonomy Of Technology Transfer And Possible Impacts On OECD Countries ”, Oecd (Der), North/South Technology Transfer: The Adjustments Ahead , Paris: OECD , 1982.
- Durgut , Metin, “Evolution of Science and Technology Policies”, Science and Technology Policy Research Association (Bited), National Science and Technology Policies Symposium in a Globalizing World, Işık University, Istanbul, 2000.
- Ekinci, Mehmet Behzat, “The Institutional Development and Financial Problems of SMEs in Turkey”, Askon Research Reports, Istanbul, 2003.
- Elmaci, Orhan; Niyazi Kurnaz, “Activity Based Costing (Ftm) Approach in Searching for a Vision for Sustainable Competitiveness ”, Id =270 & İnteditorid =28, (Accessed on 23.12.2009).
- Kosgeb (2010a), [www.İmes.Kosgeb.Gov.Tr](http://www.imes.kosgeb.gov.tr) , (Access Date 06.01.2010).
- Mulero , Mendigori , E. , June 2005. Content Validation Of A Measure Of R8td Effectiveness , Rcd Management, Vol . 35, no. 3, 311-331.
- Nieto , M. , February 2003. From Rd Management To Knowledge Management: An Overview Of Studies Of Innovation Management, Technological Forecasting And Social Change , Vol . 70, no. 2, 135-161(27).
- Nooteboom , B. , 1994. Innovation And Diffusion In Small Firms : Theory

- And Evidence , Small Business Economies , 327-348.
- Ogawa , S. , Batteries, FT, Reducing the Risks Of New Products , MIT Sloan Management Review , Vol.47 , No2, Cambridge.
- Ostim Newspaper (2009), <http://Www.Ostimgazetesi.Com/Article.Asp?Intarticle>
- Ozcan, G. , B., Small Firms And Local Economic Development, Aldershot : Avebury , Ashgate Publishing Limited, 1995.
- Pilai , AS ., Joshi , A., Rao , KS, 2002. Performance Measurement Of R&D Projects In A Multi-Project, Concurrent Engineering Environment, International Journal of Project Management.
- Romer Paul M. , “ Increasing Returns And Long Run Growth ”, Journal Of Political Economy , 94(5), 1986, Pp.1002-37.
- Sariaslan Halil, Small and Medium Sized Enterprises in Turkish Economy, Problems and New Strategies in Manufacturing Industry Enterprises, Tobb Publication, Ankara, 1996.
- Sarisoy İdris, A Comparative Analysis of Incentives for Research and Development Activities, Ekin Publishing House, Bursa, 2012.
- Economy in the World in the Transition to Information Economy , Specialization Thesis, Publication No. Dpt 2675, 2003.
- Sevüktekin Mustafa, Mehmet Nargeleçekenler , Işın Çetin, “ Socio - Economic Profile Research of Uludağ University Students” Journal of Uludağ University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Xxxı (2), 2012, pp.99-128.
- Shefer , D. , Frenkel , A., R&D, Firm Size And Innovation : An Empirical Analysis” Technovation , 25, 2005.
- Soyak Alkan, “Technological Development: An Evaluation in Terms of Neoclassical and Evolutionary Theories”, Economic Approach, 6(15), 1995, pp.93-107.
- Spencer Barbara J. , James A. Brander “International R&D Rivalry And Industrial Strategy ”, Review Of Economics Studies , 50(4),1983, Pp.707-722.
- Şimşek, M. , The Locomotives of the Economy , The Essentials of SMEs , Alfa Printing Publishing Distribution, Istanbul, 2002.

- Tüsiad Sabancı University, Competition Forum Publications, 2004. Erçağ , Mihriban, “Innovation, Technology and Research-Development Relations, A Research on R& D and Technology Acquisition Methods in the White Goods Sector in Turkey ”, Istanbul University , Department of Business Administration, Unpublished YLT, 2002.
- Uludağ, İ ., Serin, V., Small and Medium Enterprises in Turkey, İto , İstanbul, 1990.